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D6.5 Citizens and Businesses Services Optimization Pilot V1

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Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country	Project entry date	Project exit date
1	GFT ITALIA SRL	GFT	Italy		
2	STICHTING EGI	EGI	Netherlands		
3	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT	INTRA	Luxembourg		
4	SIA SPA	SIA	Italy		13/7/2022
5	NOVOTRADING LIMITED	NOVO	United Kingdom		
6	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	UNP	Portugal		
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	5
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	5
Abbreviations	6
Executive summary.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project.....	8
1.2 Description of WP6.....	9
1.3 Purpose and scope of the document	9
1.4 Structure of the document	9
2 Pilot policies.....	10
2.1 Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people	10
2.1.1 User stories	10
2.1.2 Description.....	11
2.1.3 Objective.....	11
2.1.4 Key Policy Indicator (KPI)	11
2.2 Policy Datasets.....	12
3 New Policy Making Process Definition	16
4 Feedback from Users/Stakeholders	18
4.1 Feedback Collection Plan and Methodology	18
5 Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use	20
5.1 Engagement plan and status	20
5.2 Training plan and status	22

List of Figures

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach.....	8
Figure 2. Defined Policies	12
Figure 3. Dataset folders on EGI DataHub.....	13
Figure 4. Files uploaded on EGI DataHub.....	14
Figure 5. Data connectors definition.....	14
Figure 6. Defined Datasets	15
Figure 7. New Policy Making process	16
Figure 8. List of users of the Pilot group in the VO	17

List of Tables

Table 1. List of User Stories explored in Policy #1	10
Table 2. KPI related to Policy #1	11
Table 3. Datasets associated to Policy #1.....	13
Table 4. Training Plan and Status (CDG).....	22

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI4PP	Artificial Intelligence for Public Policy
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
KPI	Key Policy Indicator
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the implementation steps of the “Citizens and Businesses Service Optimization” pilot located in Genoa, Italy. The first policy has been defined and concerns the reduction of the road accidents against vulnerable people.

According to the National Road Safety Plan, coherent with the "Safe System" proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, Genoa Municipality is focused on reducing the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030. A special attention is paid to risk categories and vulnerable targets as children and adolescents, young drivers , over -65s, cyclists, pedestrians and users of powered two-wheelers.

The objective of the policy is to determine the danger index of the city areas for vulnerable categories in relation to possible causes to decide and justify interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects.

One set of indicators were defined to estimate the risk of accidents based on AI models trained with historical data, which will help to monitor and inform about the accident risk and support the creation of tailored actions.

The relevant datasets has been defined in the VPME though the Dataset Management component under the “Citizens and Business Services Optimisation” Area and the concrete files were uploaded in the corresponding folder of the EGI DataHub, automatically created for each Dataset.

A new policy making process, based on the AI4PublicPolicy VPME, has been defined and the users registered as Policy Maker or AI Experts in the AI4PublicPolicy Virtual Organization (VO) within VPME.

The Genoa Municipality will continue to use its co-creation methodology relying on multi-actor dialogues and exchanges and collaborating with the policy beneficiaries (mainly citizens and businesses) and municipal officers to further guide the design and implementation process, taking inspiration from the diverse insights provided by the different roles and therefore getting a more holistic views of what the service should be shaped

The project seeks to enhance the civic engagement to the policy development cycle and increase the transparency and trust in the policy-making processes. AI4PublicPolicy solutions are developed based on a co-creation approach that engages the local ecosystems in the policy development activities. Hence, the involvement of local stakeholders, including potential VPME users, AI experts, decision makers and higher management officers in public administrations, social groups and NGOs, is intrinsic to the VPME implementation, pilot usage and evaluation.

The engagement of stakeholders from the local ecosystems where pilot partners are positioned is parallel to the three phases of the project work plan.

The training needs of different stakeholders are described. To this end, group and/or one-on-one dedicated sessions (as described in 4.1) will be carried on after the integrated VPME solutions become available.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP6

The WP6 is the pilot's work-package that will be devoted to deploying, operating, validating and evaluating the pilot systems with the active engagement of the public authorities of the consortium.

The main objectives are as follow:

- Undertake preparatory activities at the five (5) pilot sites towards their readiness for the pilot operations.
- Customise and deploy the AI4PublicPolicy outcomes in-line with the requirements and needs of the 5 pilot sites.
- Operate and validate the AI4PublicPolicy platform in different use cases and contexts in the 5 pilot sites.
- Evaluate the pilot systems from a technical and a business perspective.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the document

This deliverable will be devoted to the integration, deployment and operation of the project's pilot systems and policies. The work will involve tailoring and customization of the AI4PublicPolicy platform and tools to the needs of the pilot, including the implementation of pilot specific data models and features, as well as connectors to the data sources of the pilot.

The operation of the system will engage relevant stakeholders, including citizens, experts, and businesses. The task will continually improve the implementation and operation of the pilot systems and policies based on feedback from user studies and focus groups (as described in Task 2.6).

1.4 Structure of the document

This document is comprised of the following sections:

- **Section 1: Introduction** – This section presents an introduction to the project, the W6, the purpose and scope of the current document as well as its structure.
- **Section 2: Pilot policies** – contains all the details (policy name, user story, description, objective and KPIs) regarding the pilot policies that will be deployed for the pilot. In addition, the policy datasets are fully described. Finally, a demonstration of the definition of the policies and datasets with the usage of the Policy and Data Management Component is provided.
- **Section 3: New Policy Making Process Definition** – defines the new organisation processes that need to be in place in order to implement the new pilot policies. Moreover, it contains all details on how the various components of the VPME will be incorporated in the process and how the VPME will be used in the new policy making process; A screenshot of the single Virtual Organisation is provided.
- **Section 4: Feedback from Users/Stakeholders** – describes the methodologies that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders; Screenshots from surveys created with the Policy Evaluation toolkit will be shown.
- **Section 5: Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use** – demonstrates the methodologies that will be followed to engage stakeholders in the internal implementation and usage of the VPME. Furthermore, pilots also describe the steps needed to be taken in order to train the stakeholders.

2 Pilot policies

2.1 Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people

All the details of the first policy defined are reported in this section, such as the co-created User Stories that helped to shape and refine the policy, its description and goals, and the key indicators that will allow for its evaluation, application, and monitoring.

2.1.1 User stories

As per Section 4.6 of D2.1, the User Stories that are related to this Policy are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. List of User Stories explored in Policy #1

User Stories ID	As a «type of user», ... <i>Identify the customer job(s) to which this user story relates.</i>	... I want « <u>some goal</u> » ... <i>Describe the intended goal that the user expects to be fulfilled.</i>	... so that « <u>some reason</u> ». <i>Identify the reason(s) to which this user story relates.</i>
US27	Policy Officer	Systematising data from different institutional sources	I can compose complex scenarios to identify risk locations or dynamics
US28	Policy Officer	Measuring the main indicators of road accidents	I can monitor the phenomenon and the incidence of actions taken and increase the knowledge and awareness of internal and external stakeholders
US29	Policy Officer	Involving citizens in surveying and assessing the danger of city areas	I can increase the perception of risk and the sharing of actions taken
US30	Citizen	Receiving information on the danger of city areas	I can increase my perception of risk and implement behaviour aimed at reducing the probability of an accident
US31	Citizen	Being involved in the hazard assessment of city areas	I can give my contribution by providing relevant information that is not available from institutional or sensor data

US32	Citizen	Being involved in the assessment of the hazard of city areas	I can give my opinion on the results and the actions to be taken
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2.1.2 Description

According to the National Road Safety Plan, coherent with the "Safe System" proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, Genoa Municipality is focused on reducing the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030. A special attention is paid to risk categories and vulnerable targets as children and adolescents, young drivers, over -65s, cyclists, pedestrians and users of powered two-wheelers.

2.1.3 Objective

The objective of the policy is to determine the danger index of the city areas for vulnerable categories in relation to possible causes to decide and justify interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects.

2.1.4 Key Policy Indicator (KPI)

One set of indicators were defined to estimate the risk of accidents based on AI models trained with historical data, which will help to monitor and inform about the accident risk and support the creation of tailored actions.

Table 2. KPI related to Policy #1

KPI	KPI Description
road death risk	Risk to have a road accident with the death of a vulnerable subject
road injury risk	Risk to have a road accident with the injury of a vulnerable subject
road injury cost	Total cost for road accidents against vulnerable subject

The Policy has been defined in the VPME through the Policy management component under the "Citizens and Business Services Optimisation" Area.

Areas

Holistic and Accessible Urban Mobility

Data-Driven Water Infrastructure Planning and Maintenance

Citizens and Business Services Optimisation

Management and Optimisation of City Resources

Energy Management

POLICIES

Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people [More Information](#)

According to the National Road Safety Plan, coherent with the "Safe System" proposed by the European Commission and the UN 2030 Agenda, Genoa Municipality is focused on reducing the number of road fatalities and serious injuries by 50% by 2030. A special attention is payed to risk categories and vulnerable targets as children and adolescents, young drivers , over -65s, cyclists, pedestrians and users of powered two-wheelers

Datasets: AMT Stops, Green Areas, Roads, Meteo Data, Cycle paths, Schools, Accidents

Reducing road accidents against vulnerable people

Objective: To determine the danger index of the city areas for vulnerable categories in relation to possible causes to decide and justify interventions for reducing road accidents against vulnerable subjects

KPIs	
Name	Value
road death risk	
road injury risk	
road injury cost	

Metadata	
Version	Category
1.0	mobility

Figure 2. Defined Policies

2.2 Policy Datasets

In this section, the details for all the datasets relevant to the policy under evaluation, described in 2.1, are provided:

Table 3. Datasets associated to Policy #1

Name	Description	Source	Source type
Accidents	Data about accident collected from Verbatel Application	File	csv
Meteo Data	Meteo Data collected by several data logger installed on Genova municipality territory	File	csv
AMT stops	Data set on the AMT Bus stops	File	csv
Green Areas	GIS layer with city green areas	File	ShapeFile
Roads	GIS layer with city roads	File	ShapeFile
Cycle paths	GIS layer with cycle paths	File	ShapeFile
Schools	GIS layer with schools	File	ShapeFile
City areas	GIS layer with the city areas	File	ShapeFile

The Datasets has been defined in the VPME though the Dataset Management component under the “Citizens and Business Services Optimisation” Area and the concrete files were uploaded in the corresponding folder of the EGI DataHub, automatically created for each Dataset.

Figure 3. Dataset folders on EGI DataHub

Figure 4. Files uploaded on EGI DataHub

In the very next future, a set of APIs will be implemented to connect each Data Source and the connectors will be defined in the VPME through the Dataset Management component (see Figure 5).

Upload a dataset file from an endpoint

Area

-- Select an area --

Dataset

Select the area

Endpoint

Indicate the http endpoint where your dataset file is available.

Submit

Figure 5. Data connectors definition

Figure 6 shows the list of Datasets created for the Pilot with the detail of the files uploaded for the Accidents Datasets.

Areas

<p>Citizens and Business Services Optimisation</p>		
<p>Energy Management</p>		

DATASETS

<p>AMT Stops Data set on the AMT (company holding the concession for public transport) bus stops</p>	Language: Italian	Format: csv
<p>Green Areas GIS layer with city green areas</p>		Format: shapefile
<p>Roads GIS layer with city roads</p>		Format: shapefile
<p>Meteo Data Meteo Data collected by several data logger installed on Genova municipality territory</p>	Language: Italian	Format: csv
<p>Cycle paths GIS layer with cycle paths</p>		Format: shapefile
<p>Schools GIS layer with schools</p>		Format: shapefile
<p>Accidents Data about accident collected from Verbatal Application</p>	Language: Italian	Format: csv

<p>City areas GIS layer with the city areas</p>	Format: shapefile
--	-------------------

FILES

<p>new_incidenti2022.xlsx</p>	Download
<p>new_incidenti2021.xlsx</p>	Download
<p>new_incidenti2019.xlsx</p>	Download

Figure 6. Defined Datasets

3 New Policy Making Process Definition

Figure 7 shows the new Policy Making process based on the AI4PublicPolicy VPME.

Figure 7. New Policy Making process

Starting from the Data sources defined in paragraph 2.2 and the Citizens' reports and suggestions that will be collected through the integration with the SegnalaCi application the policy model will be defined in the VPME by the Policy Makers of the Mobility Department through the Policy management component (1).

Then a team of authorized AI experts will evaluate the problem described in the policy model and work on it through the Policy Extraction toolkit (2), generating the AI models to predict or optimize the Key Policy Indicators and the dashboards to interact with the AI models for evaluating and simulating the Policy (3).

Citizens and other stakeholders will be involved in the evaluation phase through surveys (4) and their feedback (5) will be taken into account to determine the impact of the different policy alternatives (6).

Finally, the evidence-based policy recommendations will be presented by the Mobility Department Policy Makers to the City Council (7). Once approved (8) they will be applied and officially communicated to the citizens.

To **define, extract, test and evaluate policies**, the users must be registered in the EGI Community, through the EGI Check-in service, and ask to join the AI4PublicPolicy Virtual Organization (VO) specifying the role (Policy Maker or AI Expert) and the pilot group within VPME. More details on the onboarding phase could be found in deliverable D5.10 "Virtualized Policy Management Environment V1". The group for Genoa Pilot was created inside the VO and the list of current users can be seen in the following figure:

The screenshot shows the 'EGI User Community' interface. At the top, there is a breadcrumb trail: 'Home > EGI User Community > My Population'. Below this is the title 'EGI User Community People'. There are two controls: 'Toggle All: Open Closed' and 'Sort By: ▲ Name Status Created Modified'. A search filter section contains fields for 'Given Name', 'Family Name', and 'Email', and a dropdown for 'Identifier' set to 'Active'. A 'CLEAR' button and a 'FILTER' button are also present. Below the filter is a navigation bar with letters from 'a' to 'z' and a search icon. The main content is a table of users:

Name (with expand icon)	Role	Status	Action
▶ Mauri Bernardoni (mbernardoni@comune.genova.it)	Policy Maker	Active	Edit
▶ Christina Katsikari (christina@reportbrain.com)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Luca Marangoni (luca.marangoni@ai4publicpolicy.eu)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Alessandro Marceddu (alessandro.marceddu@ai4publicpolicy...)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Massimo Miccoli (massimo.miccoli@ai4publicpolicy.eu)	AI Expert	Active	Edit
▶ Alessandra Riso (risso.alessandra@gmail.com)	Policy Maker	Active	Edit

Figure 8. List of users of the Pilot group in the VO

4 Feedback from Users/Stakeholders

In this section, the methods that will be adopted to collect feedback from citizens and other relevant stakeholders are described.

4.1 Feedback Collection Plan and Methodology

The Genoa Municipality will continue to use its co-creation methodology relying on multi-actor dialogues and exchanges and collaborating with the policy beneficiaries (mainly citizens and businesses) and municipal officers to further guide the design and implementation process, taking inspiration from the diverse insights provided by the different roles and therefore getting a more holistic views of what the service should be shaped.

The following methods and tools will be explored and implemented to gather feedback from such stakeholders:

- Organisation of **Cross-Organisational Thematic Tables** linked to the topic of road accident prevention, carrying out a broad discussion on this issue, to which the CDG is particularly sensitive. It is planned to hold round tables devoted to road safety, taking as an example the one held at Palazzo Tursi during European Mobility Week. Multiple aspects of this topic will be addressed during these thematic tables, also giving ample emphasis to the CDG's Pilot in the AI4PublicPolicy project and its objectives, which fit perfectly into this broader context. Related aspects will also be addressed: in addition to the numbers and costs of road accidents, consideration will also be given, for instance, to how the maintenance of ever safer roads for all can have a beneficial impact on reducing accidents, thus linking the topic to the "SegnalaCI" initiative, also carried out by the CDG. Insights on the insurance world, and representatives of active citizenship will also be brought to the table, including the in-depth discussion of road safety education in schools in cooperation with the Traffic and Local Police on safe driving. The chosen method is strictly interrelated with the co-creation workshops and the "Incidente? Pensaci Prima" Initiative, whose ultimate goal consists in encouraging the responsible and conscious behaviour when driving vehicles in order to prevent and combat alcohol- and drug-related accidents. It is expected to stimulate the awareness-raising for citizenship, especially young people, in order to influence safe driving habits, stimulate risk awareness, as well as identify and co-design new ideas and concepts about the integration of the Ai in the the mentioned use case. This initiative is implemented by the Municipality of Genoa – Municipal Police Office, together with the University of Genoa (Department of Education Sciences and Department of Architecture and Design) and the Automobile Club of Genoa.
- Other **participatory tools (like focus groups and interviews) related to the Pacts for Participatory Urban Regeneration**, with emphasis on those linked to the Pact for the Historic Centre and to the Caruggi-Umbre de' Muri Integrated Plan. This plan has the aim of redeveloping and regenerating squares and open spaces in the old city, together with the enhancement of services for discussion and exchange with citizens and education on key issues, such as road accident prevention. The proposed activities are in line with Goal 11 of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development "Making Cities and Human Settlements Inclusive" and envisage the collaboration of the relevant municipal departments on different topics: from education to mobility, from commerce to environment and territory, from heritage to tourism. This pact for participatory urban regeneration is provided for in the Regulation on collaboration between citizens and the administration for the care and regeneration and shared management of urban commons, with priority given to the most critical areas;
- **Short questionnaires via email**, consisting in awareness moments recurring to CDG's Local Police's mailing list and providing a summary of the project and CDG's pilot. A few questions (3-4) will be posed to motivate people to reflect on the importance of a responsible and conscious behaviour when driving vehicles in order to prevent and combat alcohol- and drug-related accidents visit, as well as to provide their feedback afterwards via email reply.

The respondents will be asked to join the group of beta testers (BTs) for further evaluation of policies defined under the AI4PublicPolicy;

- **Wider Survey conducted via AI4PublicPolicy App:** this will be directed to the beta testers and to the stakeholders already engaged during the co-creation phase and will consist in a more comprehensive survey, created through the Policy Evaluation Toolkit within the VPME, for gathering deeper insights and feedback.
- **Usability test and feedback focus groups or interviews:** this activity will take advantage of the co-creation workshops and will be directed to the technical validation and specialized feedback functional to the improvement of the Policy and the resource management associated with it. It will be explored whether the involved users are available to test the usability of the VPME in the definition and systematization of other policies for the respondents showing a special interest in the tools and workflow and who, in this way, will be able to contribute to further enhancement of the user experience within VPME;
- **Social media.** The CDG is also considering posting topic-oriented questions to directly extract sentiment from social media activities, such as Facebook groups and to employ text analysis algorithms for sentiment extraction for feedback collection in relation to the chosen and future policies.

The same feedback collection logic will be employed in future policies to be defined. Moreover, continuous efforts will be carried on to effectively reach out to more civil society stakeholders.

5 Stakeholders involvement in VPME pilot use

5.1 Engagement plan and status

The project seeks to enhance the civic engagement to the policy development cycle and increase the transparency and trust in the policy-making processes. AI4PublicPolicy solutions are developed based on a co-creation approach that engages the local ecosystems in the policy development activities. Hence, the involvement of local stakeholders, including potential VPME users, AI experts, decision makers and higher management officers in public administrations, social groups and NGOs, is intrinsic to the VPME implementation, pilot usage and evaluation.

The engagement of stakeholders from the local ecosystems where pilot partners are positioned is parallel to the three phases of the project work plan.

- **Phase 1 (M1-M9):** Specification & Fine Tuning of the AI4PublicPolicy Concept
- **Phase 2 (M10-M24):** Initial Integration & Technical Validation
- **Phase 3 (M25-M36):** Technical & Business Validation

Within each Phase specific objectives for the engagement of stakeholders are set based on the project’s work plan and input; and dedicated activities and outputs are provided.

Phase 1 Specification & Fine Tuning of the AI4PublicPolicy Concept

Objectives	Collect insights on the current status of production processes, as well as the challenges and potentials of introducing AI systems. Review Use Cases and reference scenarios to conclude, update and extend User Stories.	
Input	Pilot Use Cases	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	Genoa Municipality	Policy makers Municipality officers and managers Citizens & Community Groups Socially excluded groups (e.g. minorities, elderly, etc.) Public local Authorities Experts in the field of AI and Machine Learning Other stakeholders (social entrepreneurs etc.)
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Consolidated list of Use Cases & User Stories	

Phase 2 Initial Integration & Technical Validation

Objectives	Develop the preliminary proof-of-concept (PoC) of the VPME prototype demonstrators. Review and update Use Cases and user stories. Collect users’ feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept. Conduct preliminary business modelling exercise.
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Input	Pilot Use Cases	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	Genoa Municipality	Policy makers Municipality officers and managers Citizens & Community Groups Socially excluded groups (e.g. minorities, elderly, etc.) Public local Authorities Experts in the field of AI and Machine Learning Other stakeholders (social entrepreneurs etc.)
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of the prototype demonstrators Updated user stories list	

Phase 3 Technical & Business Validation

Objectives	Pilot test the integrated VPME solutions. Collect users' feedback on the preliminary demonstrators regarding user experience features, usability, security ethics and overall concept & Benchmark with previous Phase input. Validate Exploitation and sustainability pathways via the updated business modelling exercise.	
Input	Pilot Use Cases,	
Actors	Responsible(s)	Participants
	Genoa Municipality	Policy makers Citizens & Community Groups Socially excluded groups (e.g. minorities, elderly, etc.) Public local Authorities Experts in the field of AI and Machine Learning Other stakeholders (social entrepreneurs etc.)
Activities	2 Co-creation Workshops	
Outputs	Assessment of integrated VPME solutions Validated Business Models	

5.2 Training plan and status

The training needs of different stakeholders are described next. To this end, group and/or one-on-one dedicated sessions (as described in 4.1) will be carried on after the integrated VPME solutions become available.

Table 4. Training Plan and Status (CDG)

Stakeholder type	Role	Training requirements
Public and local authorities	<p>End-users (policy makers), Data providers, Feedback providers, Business opportunities, municipality officers and managers</p> <p>Authorities will help to shape up the AI4PP VPME functionalities and layouts, and the ambition of the tool based on the data availability.</p> <p>Municipality officers will recur to the VPME to inform their energy policy- and decision-making rationale.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources - VPME walkthrough - Policy definition standalone exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Genoa Municipality - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genoa Municipality team - Relevant project partners
Researchers and academia experts	<p>Expertise, Data providers, Feedback providers, Project opportunities</p> <p>Building on the science that has been produced, state-of-the-art methods and innovative products and services, the VPME improvements will benefit greatly from work sessions with the local experts on AI, ML and big data monitoring and analytics.</p> <p>R&D projects in relation to the city's policy development and implementation might also find use in the framework and components behind VPME.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources (focus on the AI model and text analysis used) - VPME walkthrough - Data Catalogue showcase - Research question exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Genoa Municipality - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genoa Municipality team - Relevant project partners
Companies and entities of the energy sector	<p>Business opportunities, Market makers, Feedback providers, Data providers</p> <p>Leveraged on the AI-based policy making, new synergies and business models, and large-scale sustainable investments, can potentially be created that help to achieve the energy and climate goals of the city.</p> <p>Products and services in relation to the city's policy development and implementation might also find use in the framework and components behind VPME.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources - VPME walkthrough - Data Catalogue showcase - Business model exercise <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Genoa Municipality - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genoa Municipality team - Relevant project partners

<p>Citizen groups and associations</p>	<p>Beneficiaries, Feedback providers.</p> <p>The community “leaders” have the potential to mobilize their networks, to promote energy literacy and capacitation, and to motivate discussions on the efficacy of local AI-based energy policy making.</p> <p>Citizens will provide input to fine-tuning the VPME, by voicing on to what level the decisions based on the tools are answering their needs.</p> <p>They do not require VPME training per se, but they must be well informed about what’s behind the tool and why they are needed.</p>	<p>Training materials?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy #1 resources (focus on mapping and text analysis) - VPME summary - Surveying and polling exercises <p>Where?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presential at their infrastructure or at Genoa Municipality - Remotely <p>Trainer?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genoa Municipality team
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